

ANALYSIS OF VIEWS ON THE ORGANIZATION OF MILITARY PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article presents an opinion on the specifics of the military pedagogical process based on an analysis of the views of scholars working in different eras and countries on the organization of the military pedagogical process.

Key words: pedagogy, military pedagogy, education, training, process, powerful, victory, strategy.

Annatsiya: ushbu maqolada turli davrlar va davlatlarda faoliyat olib borgan olimlarning harbiy pedagogik jarayonni tashkil etishga doir qarashlari tahlili asosida harbiy pedagogik jarayonning o'ziga hosligi to'g'risida fikr bildiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: pedagogika, harbiy pedagogika, ta'lim, tarbiya, jarayon, qudratli, g'alaba, strategiya.

Аннотация: в данной статье представлено мнение об уникальности военно-педагогического процесса, основанное на анализе взглядов ученых, работавших в разные периоды и странах по организации военно-педагогического процесса.

Ключевые слова: педагогика, военная педагогика, воспитание, подготовка, процесс, мощь, победа, стратегия.

Since the emergence of the army as a social entity, the training and education of military personnel, which is the most important component of military activity, has been one of the main tasks of military activity. In fact, it is one of the multifaceted necessary and mandatory aspects of practical military pedagogy, which has a special place in the fact that it is based on preparing soldiers for successful combat operations.

What is the definition of military pedagogy? Military pedagogy is a branch of pedagogical education that includes the training of military personnel and military groups during the military-pedagogical process and preparation for combat operations, successful military-professional activity and combat operations.

Initially, military pedagogy emerged as a practical activity of commanders and subordinates. Over time, the accumulated knowledge, skills and traditions

about the training and upbringing of warriors were passed down from generation to generation in the form of legends and proverbs.

As military activity became more complex (especially during the formation of powerful states), the formation of relatively large regular armies ensured the further development of military pedagogy. Our great ancestors made a great contribution to the training of future commanders, the training of warriors in combat operations and the development of the art of war, and the advancement of military pedagogy to a new level.

It is appropriate to cite Amir Temur's "Temur's Code" as a vivid example of such ancestors. The second part of the work consists of the famous Jahangir's own testament, advice and teachings. It discusses who to rely on in governing the state, the role and duties of the crown and throne holders, the selection of ministers and army leaders, the structure of the army and the rules of warfare, the procedure for governing the country, the duties and responsibilities of statesmen and army leaders, the way to reward emirs, ministers and other officials for their special services to the crown and throne, and more.

In another military theoretical view of Amir Temur in state management and military education, he constantly taught his subordinates that the organization of a new type of regular army, political organization, the subordination of all aspects of life, especially the economy, to the strategic task of achieving victory, strong discipline, compliance with the rules of military operations by each warrior, and the skillful use of diplomatic means ensure victory over the opponent.

One of the important tasks facing military management bodies in the formation of a modern army is the training and education of military personnel, that is, the formation of their professional training at a high level to fulfill their military duty to defend the Motherland. In order to fulfill this task at a high level, the qualitative organization of the military-pedagogical process by the commanders and heads of military teams based only on theoretical foundations and practical experience does not give sufficient results, and in the implementation of this task, it is important to use modern pedagogy, as well as changes in military pedagogy, which are rapidly developing, and important views on the conduct of modern battles.

The military pedagogical process is a purposeful, organized type of activity carried out by the commanders of military teams to train, educate military

personnel, units, and military teams as a whole, and prepare them for purposeful, skillful and courageous actions.

The military pedagogical process is a set of activities carried out not only in peacetime, but also during the preparation and conduct of combat operations. In this case, the military pedagogical process includes the training of military personnel in peacetime and wartime. The military pedagogical process in peacetime is a process that ensures the combat readiness of military teams, preparation for combat operations in a combat situation, and the fulfillment of assigned tasks.

In this regard, let us consider the opinions of foreign experts on the organization and conduct of the military pedagogical process.

According to Dobrodon Elena Vladimirovna, when developing a methodology for organizing the military pedagogical process and developing professional competencies, it is necessary not only to rely on a modern methodological basis, but also to take into account social reality, a person-oriented situation as the most important value, which, in turn, allows for training in accordance with the latest requirements in the field of professions, increasing the level of professional training of cadets, that is, in organizing military pedagogy, it is an important basis for developing theory and practice, training and training military personnel.

We must not forget that in the training of military personnel, it is not only the study or consideration of the pedagogical experience of developed countries, but also the widespread use of national values and traditions when organizing the pedagogical process is one of the directions for achieving high results*.

According to A.S. Vershkov, in the organization of the military pedagogical process, mainly military pedagogical experience is of great professional, methodological and scientific importance in the framework of scientific and methodological seminars, exchange of experience, round tables, master classes and creative lectures.

In addition, in the conditions of the digital transformation of education, the activity of a teacher is not only an urgent, but also a required problem, the analysis of which allows combining the achievements of the design of pedagogical processes and electronic didactics. In this regard, the researcher emphasizes that organized training in the combination of the personal qualifications of a military teacher and the electronic learning system is an effective way to achieve the intended goal.

*-The author's opinion on the idea:

In organizing the military pedagogical process, master classes between educational institutions, participation in joint trainings, and the exchange of skills of military educators create the basis for achieving good results and diversifying and developing the military pedagogical process. *

Nurmukhammad Mahkamov believes that the organization of military pedagogy, further improving the education and training of military personnel in modern conditions, the study of the richest experiences, the use of new methods of generalizing the theory and practice of training military personnel, the development of the theory and practice of teaching serve as the basis for education and upbringing.

In organizing the military pedagogical process, it is advisable not only to study the experiences of developed countries, but also to take into account the relevance, moral relevance, compliance not only with modern requirements, but also with the views of the nation, the foreign and domestic policy of the state, and to apply them to the educational process through long observations and analyses.*

D. Shirley emphasized that military pedagogy has two distinct differences from other educational pedagogies: military pedagogy requires teaching and learning to take place in a military environment, and military pedagogy applies teaching and learning to situations intended for military purposes, therefore, in organizing military pedagogy, it is more appropriate to take into account the professional training of soldiers and organize education based on the specialization of those who study.

However, we should not forget that the concepts of “general military pedagogy, special military pedagogy”, which are one of the golden rules in the organization of military service and military pedagogy in general, exist. In this case, we should not forget that general pedagogical training and special pedagogical training differ from each other, and the conditions for organizing them based on the requirements of pedagogical training*.

A. Lopukha, D. Suslov, E. Solomatin believe that the creation of theoretical and value foundations of military-pedagogical training of military personnel, the main directions of the progressive development of the military education system and the role of military pedagogical education in this, as well as the combination of military pedagogy and psychology, are the conceptual basis for the development of the military education system, and that not only pedagogical views, but also the role of psychology are important in the development of military education.

The separation of military pedagogy from military psychology, their formation as a separate discipline, is certainly an indication of the development of these disciplines.

But we must not forget that military pedagogy and psychology are inextricably linked in the training of military personnel, their formation as excellent, mature specialists of their profession, which has a special place in the military pedagogical process and is one of the fronts that must be carried out in one way or another. *

Kodines V.A. Naumlyuk A.G. The military-pedagogical process is a purposeful and organized type of activity carried out by commanders, headquarters, bodies directly involved in working with personnel to train military personnel, units and military teams in general, to educate them in a purposeful and courageous manner, and to prepare them for combat operations. In peacetime, it is defined as the activities of military teams aimed at ensuring their combat readiness, preparing and conducting combat operations in a combat situation, and performing tasks. The military-pedagogical process is a complex social phenomenon that includes military education and upbringing, which are inextricably linked to each other. Military training is understood as an organized and purposeful process of providing combatants with military knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for practical activities, as well as the preparation and education of military groups (teams) for the implementation of combat operations (combat missions).

The organization of combat, spiritual, educational and professional training of military personnel and their formation as professional specialists is defined as one of the main tasks of commanders at all levels. Therefore, the responsibility for the timely organization and purposeful implementation of professional training of all military personnel, units and military teams is borne by commanders and chiefs*.

Kozhevin, D. M. The pedagogical process in the development of discipline among cadets should be characterized by expediency, duality and integrity. The expediency of the pedagogical process means the subordination of its content, methods, tasks and forms of interaction to a specific goal, that is, the development and improvement of professional and moral principles among military personnel. In particular, the formation of discipline. The duality of the pedagogical process means the presence of two interrelated active sides in it. On the one hand, there

is a teacher who creates all possible conditions for the development of discipline, and on the other hand, the cadet's activity is aimed at adopting the norms, knowledge and values offered by the teacher.

How important is the place and role of the teacher in organizing the military pedagogical process in military communities. In the military pedagogical process, the teacher must provide not only education, but also upbringing continuously.

In organizing the pedagogical process, the teacher must have not only knowledge as a specialist, but also the skills formed as a teacher, which is sufficient, only then can the teacher not only provide knowledge to the students, but also provide educational standards formed on the basis of national values.

Considering the opinions of currently active military specialists, we can see that in almost all countries, the organization of military pedagogy (education) and the implementation of the pedagogical process are practically the same, and are determined by the study of rich experience in organizing military education, the generalization of theory and practice, the personal skills of the military educator and the formation of modern educational technologies, pedagogy and psychology.

In conclusion, in a period when new and innovative methods of technology are not limited to the sphere of scientific and technical progress, but also penetrate all spheres of education, the volume of information has increased dramatically, the development of science and technology has increased dramatically, especially the use of remote-controlled enemy detection systems, the use of modern weapons and military equipment on the battlefield, the methods and methods of their use have changed radically, and information detection, processing and transmission centers have been equipped, the need to fundamentally reform the content of training, which is the main link of the military education system, and to improve the activities of the training leader at a high level, has become even more urgent.

References:

1. Temur tuzuklari //Forschadan| A. Soguniy va H. Karomatov tarj; B. Ahmedov tahrir. ostida/.- T.: Nashriyot-matbaa birlashmasi, 1991.- 144 b.
2. Amir Temurning ma'anaviyat, ma'rifat va ta'lim-tarbiya haqidagi ta'limoti asoslari.

3. Добродон Ye.B. Современная военная педагогика: проблемы и перспективы / Вестник Донецкого педагогического института, 2018. – С.122.
4. КиберЛенинка. Военно-педагогический опыт как важнейший компонент деятельности преподавателя ведомственного вуза в условиях цифровой трансформации образования А.С. Вершков.
5. Jamiyat va innovatsiyalar – Общество и инновации – Society and innovations Special issue -1, №01 (2020).
6. D. Shirli Военная психология и педагогика / Под ред. В. Ф. Кулакова. М.: Совершенство, 1998. 140 с.
7. А.Лопуха., Д.Суслов. Методология и методы психолого-педагогического исследования. М.: Академия, 2001., 162 с.
8. А.Лопуха., Д.Суслов. Методология и методы психолого-педагогического исследования. М.: Академия, 2001., 162 с.
9. XIV Международная студенческая научная конференция. В.А. Кодинец, А.Г. Наумлюк Организация военно-педагогического процесса в части.
10. Д. М. Кожевин, Характеристика педагогического процесса. Воспитание дисциплинированности среди курсантов ввузов / Д. М. Кожевин.- Текст: непосредственный // Молодой ученый. - 2022. - № 20 (415).
11. Tursunov Abdumomin Science and innovation international scientific journal 2022 № 3

